

Familial amyloid polyneuropathy (FAP) clusters are located at ancient mining districts: A possible geochemical origin of the disease

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Abstract: Familial Amyloid Polyneuropathy (FAP) is an endemic amyloidosis involving harmful aggregation of proteins, most commonly transthyretin (TTR) but sometimes also apolipoprotein A-1 or gelsolin. TTR FAP appears to be transmitted as an autosomal dominant trait. Over 100 point mutations have been identified, with the Val30Met substitution being the most common. Yet, the mechanism of pathogenesis and the overall origin of FAP remain unclear. Here, we argue that FAP could be related to harmful metal exposure. FAP incidence is unevenly distributed over the planet, and the three largest defined clusters exist in Japan, Portugal, and Sweden. All three disease regions are also ancient mining districts, with associated metal contamination of the local environment. There are two main mechanisms for how harmful metals, after uptake into tissues and body fluids, could induce FAP. First, the metals could directly influence the expression, function, and/or aggregation of the proteins involved in FAP pathology, and these particular metal-protein interactions might constitute molecular targets for anti-FAP drug design. Second, metal exposure could induce FAP-associated genetic mutations, which may have happened several generations ago. These two mechanisms can occur in parallel. In conclusion, the possibility that FAP could be related to metal exposure in geochemically defined regions deserves further attention.

Keywords: Neurodegeneration; protein aggregation; proteinopathy; metal-protein binding; metal toxicity

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Familial Amyloid Polyneuropathy (FAP) is an endemic amyloidosis with variable clinical presentations characterized by aggregation of proteins into harmful amyloid material. The most common aggregating protein is transthyretin (TTR), but aggregates of apolipoprotein A-1 and gelsolin are also observed (Plante-Bordeneuve and Said, 2011). For TTR FAP, the initial symptoms are loss of pain and temperature sensation in the feet caused by a length-dependent neuropathy, evolving into muscle weakness and paresis of feet and legs, autonomic failure with gastrointestinal symptoms, cardiomyopathy (Plante-Bordeneuve and Said, 2011), and finally sphincter weakness and sexual dysfunction (Lopes et al., 2017). First symptoms appear at about 30 years of age, and the survival time is highly variable but on average ten years from diagnosis (Plante-Bordeneuve and Said, 2011). As TTR is mainly produced in the liver, orthotopic liver transplantations have been tried in order to eliminate the source of TTR, with variable success (Benson, 2013). Furthermore, TTR is one of the few amyloid proteins for which the US Food and Drug Administration has approved aggregation-inhibiting drugs (Yokoyama and Mizuguchi, 2020), such as the molecule tafamidis which binds to the TTR thyroxine binding site and stabilizes the generally non-aggregating tetrameric TTR conformation (Bulawa et al., 2012).

TTR FAP appears to be transmitted as an autosomal dominant trait. The most common mutation is the Val30Met substitution, although more than 100 other amyloidogenic point mutations (Araki and Ando, 2010) have been described at various geographic locations across the world (Fig 1). Yet, some individuals with the TTR mutation never develop FAP (Sekijima, 2001) and a few patients with FAP do not show any family history of the disease (Sekijima, 2001). To what extent an environmental component contributes to FAP seems unresolved (Gonzalez-Duarte et al., 2012). Even though significant progress has been made in understanding - and treating - FAP at the molecular level, the mechanism of pathogenesis and the overall origin of the disease remain unclear (Benson and Kincaid, 2007; Tseng et al., 2023).

Here, we argue that FAP could be related to harmful metal exposure. FAP incidence is unevenly distributed over the planet (Fig. 1), and the three largest defined clusters exist in Japan, northern Portugal, and northern Sweden (Andrade, 1952; Araki and Ando, 2010; Plante-Bordeneuve and Said, 2011; Hellman and Suhr, 2012). In our opinion, it is probably not a coincidence that all these three regions are also ancient mining districts.

In Japan, three distinctive endemic FAP foci have been described: Arao city in the Kumamoto prefecture, Ogawa village in the Nagano prefecture, and Noto peninsula in the Ishikawa prefecture (Araki and Ando, 2010). Japan is perforated with coal mines and mines for metals such as As, Au, Cd, Cr, Cu, Fe, Hg, Mn, Ni, Pb, Sn, U, and W. Specifically, Arao has been a mining town since the 18th century with seven mines within the city itself, and Arao also has the largest coal mine harbour in Japan, i.e. the Port of Miike. The small mountain village of Ogawa is located at the confluence of several water streams draining the surrounding volcanic slopes. The Noto peninsula hosts the historical Togi metal mining fields (Hamida et al., 2022) together with the Searashi Mn mine at the volcanic regions of the Noto peninsula Ishikawa prefecture. The geological rationale for all these mines is that Japan is located where the Eurasian tectonic plate met the Izanagi plate some 70 million years ago. It should be noted that coal mining is associated with the release of metals with genotoxic properties (Kopp et al., 2018), often found in elevated concentrations in coal mine tailings and waste, and leaching into agricultural soils typically in a concentration sequence of As > Zn > Ni > Cd > Cr > Cu > Pb (Li et al., 2019). Coal often also contains U (Lauer et al., 2017) with known neurotoxic and genotoxic properties (Berntsson et al., 2023).

In Portugal, FAP is known as *Mal dos pèsinhos* or Foot-disease, which originally was described among fishermen from Póvoa de Varzim north of Porto (Andrade, 1952). However, the entire northern coast of Portugal presents cases, and this is the location of the largest FAP cluster in the world (Plante-Bordeneuve and Said, 2011). Portugal is located in a geological zone with diverse mineral deposits and possible tectonic activity (Duarte et al., 2013), where deposits of Sn, U, and W are present in the

northern regions. Abandoned U mines are located east of Póvoa de Varzim, where runoffs may contaminate the groundwater and drain into the ocean. The environmental exposure is likely increased by the use of agricultural fertilizers, which are known to increase the solubility of U and its leach into the environment (Nolan et al., 2015). The Atlantic ocean west of Portugal is a seismically active zone where the Azores-Gibraltar Transform Fault Zone (AGFZ) has produced several large-magnitude earthquakes and volcanoes. In the original description of FAP from Portugal (Andrade, 1952), the index case fisherman describes ingestion of large quantities of sea water in a drowning accident before deterioration of symptoms. No data on metal concentrations in the ocean above the AGFZ exist, but measurements in the Ave river flowing through Povo de Varzim into the ocean have shown significantly elevated concentrations of neurotoxic metals (Soares et al., 1999). To what extent these high metal concentrations emanate from volcanic rock along the AGFZ, or from metal exposure from textile, tanning, plastic, metal plating and rubber industries in the region remains to elucidate. Either way, the possibility that Portugise FAP fishermen families have been subject to metal exposure from the waters west of Povo de Varzim should be further explored.

In Sweden, a distinctive FAP cluster exists in the northern municipality of Skellefteå (Plante-Bordeneuve and Said, 2011; Hellman and Suhr, 2012), where mining activities for Ag, As, Au, Cu, Pb, and Zn can be dated back to the 18th century. Twenty-eight different metal mines have been opened in the Skellefteå mining district, which holds massive sulfide deposits hosted in metavolcanic rocks. U minerals are also present (Weihed et al., 1992). Sweden is located in the region of Baltic bedrock, and therefore geologically stable. But in a palaeotectonic context the Skellefteå district has been a collision site for tectonic plates (Weihed et al., 1992), akin to the situation in Japan, which explains the large amounts of minerals present.

If we accept the idea that FAP could be related to exposure to harmful metals, there are two main mechanisms for how that may happen. The first scenario is that after uptake into tissues and body fluids, the metals could directly influence the expression,

function, and/or aggregation of the proteins involved in FAP pathology, i.e. TTR, apolipoprotein A-1, and gelsolin. The second scenario is that metal exposure could induce the genetic mutations associated with FAP, such as the TTR Val30Met mutation. A combination of the two mechanisms is also possible. In the second scenario, the disease-related mutations may have occurred several generations ago. The general conclusion would then be that exposure to neurotoxic and genotoxic metals from mining activities can induce adverse health effects, but this is not a novel observation. In the first scenario, however, the damaging metal-protein interactions are continually ongoing in FAP patients. The first line of defence against such possibly damaging interactions is prevention of metal exposure, however in already exposed people these particular metal-protein interactions would constitute molecular targets for anti-FAP drug design. In conclusion, the possibility that FAP might be related to metal exposure in geochemically defined regions deserves further attention.

Figure 1. A.) Distribution of FAP clusters across the world. B.) Distribution of FAP cases in Japan, together with observed point mutations in the TTR protein. Image by PR, based on Figs. 1 & 2 in Araki & Ando, 2010 (Araki and Ando, 2010).

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Data Availability: All datasets generated during and/or analyzed during the current study are included in the manuscript.

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